

Use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in teaching English

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Annotation. Today, the use of modern pedagogical technologies has become a great demand in modern education. This method has been found to be especially effective in teaching a foreign language. This article discusses in detail the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in teaching English.

Keywords: English, foreign language teaching method, pedagogical technologies, curriculum, training mechanism, etc.

In recent years, the issue of using new modern technologies for teaching foreign languages in the Institution of Higher Education has been increasingly raised. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, and a new approach to the learning process. In modern pedagogical practice, various teaching technologies are used, with the help of which the interest of students to the subject increases sharply; the academic performance and the level of intellectual culture are also increased. One of the main tasks of the research is to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each student, to choose such teaching methods that would allow each student to show his activity, his creativity, and also to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies such as training in cooperation, project methodology, the use of new information and communication technologies, and the Internet resources help to realize a person-oriented approach to teaching, provide individualization and differentiation of education, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of education, and inclinations. Results of the research and their discussion.

In the framework of achieving the aim of the research, it was found out by me that in the process of application of information technologies by the teacher of the foreign language, students realize creative activities that include the ability to question, explain, study, describe, compare, analyze, evaluate, express their opinions and judgments, argue them, conduct independent searches for necessary information, navigate the text in English, and to make brief messages on a given topic. All of the above will allow students to use the acquired knowledge and skills in practical activities and daily life to communicate with representatives of other countries; receive information from foreign sources of the information needed for educational purposes; expand opportunities in choosing future professional activities; study the values of the world culture, cultural heritage and achievements of other countries; familiarize representatives of foreign countries with the culture and achievements of Russia. The use of information technology

elements in classes helps to form the ability of schoolchildren to work with various information, critical attitude towards it, develops logical thinking, provides information and emotional saturation of lessons, promotes interest of students to the subject, and activates their creative potential with the surrounding life. The use of computer and information technologies in the second and third levels of training allows students to prepare better for the final certification in English in accordance with the requirements of the state standard. In the process of training: students not only improve the knowledge they acquired during the previous period of training, but also expand their vocabulary taking into account the practical knowledge of a foreign language in the standard situations (within the framework of monologue utterances with elements of reasoning and dialogical conversations in the form of an exchange of views). At present, various forms of organization of the educational process are used.

Modern technologies in education are viewed as means by dint of which a new educational paradigm can be realized. The most general interpretation of the concept "technology" consists in the fact that it represents scientifically and practically grounded system of activity, which is applied by a man for the purpose of transformation of the environment, production of material or spiritual values. V. P. Bepal'ko notes that any activity can be either a technology or an art. An art is based on intuition, a technology – on science. Everything begins with an art, and ends with a technology for the purpose of beginning again. Any planning, without which in you can't do the pedagogical activity, conflicts with an impromptu, acting by intuition, and therefore can be considered as the beginning of technology. Since information technologies are both a means of supplying material and a controlling agent – such technologies provide high quality of the material supply and use various communication channels (text, sound, graphic, and touch). All this allows increasing students' motivation and forming their communicative competence. The computer at the lessons of a foreign language makes it possible to implement a personality-oriented approach to learning, provides for individualization and differentiation of instruction, increases activity, motivates students, intensifies the learning process, fosters adequate self-esteem for students, and provides them with a comfortable learning environment.

In the pedagogical science and practice one can reveal the existence of various interpretations of pedagogical technology. And it is not casual, as every author comes up to understanding of the essence of technology in general proceeding from the certain conceptual approach. However all existent positions are characterized by the following points:

- a technology is purposefully developed for the certain pedagogical intention, in its basis there is a methodological, philosophical position of the author;
- a technological chain of actions and operations is arranged strictly in accordance with objectives, which have a form of a concrete expected result;

- functioning of a technology envisages the interrelated activity of a teacher with students on a contractual basis taking into account principles of individualization and differentiation, optimal realization of human and technical possibilities, use of dialogue and communication;
- the stage-by-stage planning and successive embodiment of the elements of a pedagogical technology must be, from one side, reproduced by any teacher and, from the other, guarantee the achievement of the planned results by all students;
- the organic part of any pedagogical technology consists in diagnostic procedures, containing the criteria, indexes and instruments of measurement of the results of activity.

Technology of development of critical thinking is the foundation for mastering of new types of activity. The subject of any new pedagogical technology is concrete co-operations of students and teachers in different types of activity, which are organized on the base of accurate structuring, systematization, programming, algorithmization, standardization of methods and techniques of teaching or educating, with introduction of computerization and technique facilities. Thus, modern pedagogical technologies realize the syllabus and provide the achievement of the set didactic objectives in a new way, implying the scientific approaches to the organization of educational process in the institute of higher learning. They extend the range of educational services offered to students, change and provide new forms, methods and means of education. Use of modern pedagogical technologies is one of the most promising directions of the development of higher education, which promote more profound individualization and intensification of educational process, shaping and self-actualization of the personality of a future specialist.

References:

3. PQ 1875 “Chet tillarni o’rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to’g’risida” gi qaror. “Xalq so’zi” gazetasi, 2-bet. 2012 yil,10-dekabr
4. Boswood, T. (1997). *New Ways of Using Computers in Language Teaching* (New Ways in Tesol Series II), California: Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages. 3.Harmer, J. (2007). *How to teach English*, Harlow, Essex: Pearson-Longman
6. Warschauer, M., & Kern, K. (2000). *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
7. Bekmuratova U. B. “Ingliz tilini o’qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish” mavzusida referat. Toshkent — 2012 yil Отабоева, М. Р. Chet tilini o’qitishda zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalaridan foydalanish va uning samaradorligi / M. P. Отабоева.

8. N. Q. Xatamova, M.N.mirzayeva. "INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA QO'LLANILADIGAN INTERFAOL USULLAR" (uslubiy qo'llanma), Navoiy, 2006, 40 bet.
9. M. Xoldorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. "CHET TILINI O'QITISHDA YORDAMCHI VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH". Toshkent: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU, 2005
10. O'.Hoshimov, I. Yoqubov. "INGLIZ TILI O'QITISH METODIKASI" (o'quv qo'llanma) Toshkent: "Sharq" nashriyoti, 2003